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Non-Suicidal Self-Injury Behavior and Disengagement Coping of Recollect University Students

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Abstract

The prevalence of self-harm, specifically among emerging adults, has been on the rise. However, most studies focus on suicide and less on NSSI, especially that of senior high school and college students. Moreover, developing countries have minimal studies on NSSI (Costa et al., 2021). Cognizant of the dangers NSSI can pose to students' well-being, this study sought to discover the relationship between non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) and disengagement coping among 364 students from recollect Universities. The survey instruments used were the Non-Suicidal Self-Injury Assessment Tool (NSSI-AT) and the Coping Strategies Inventory to measure NSSI and disengagement coping, respectively. The study employed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test to determine necessary data measures and assess the normality of the variables, wherein weighted means were used to determine the level of non-suicidal self-injury and disengagement coping. On the other hand, Spearman's rank correlation assessed their relationship. Results show low NSSI behavior among the participants across sex, ordinal position, and family structure. Disengagement coping is moderate across demographics except for students in a family structure with a single parent. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient showed a positive moderate correlation between NSSI and disengagement coping. The reasons why students living with a single-parent family structure have high levels of disengagement coping were also discussed. Thus, improved student services using a multi-pronged approach is recommended, which may include the administration's increased awareness initiatives as well as preventive policies and strengthening teachers' and counselors' involvement.

Keywords: *non-suicidal self-injury, disengagement coping, adolescent students*

Introduction

Adolescence is characterized by rapid social, physiological, and psychological development, involving the formation of individual identities, the pursuit of independence, and testing personal abilities. During this phase, adolescents undergo significant internal changes driven by fluctuating neurotransmitter release in the brain. Additionally, the prefrontal cortex, which is accountable for problem-solving, is still maturing (Cassels & Wilkinson, 2016). Consequently, it is not surprising that adolescence is often associated with the emergence of non-suicidal self-injury cases and other psychological difficulties (Moutier, 2021).

Non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI, as defined by Moutier (2021), is an act of intentionally hurting oneself, causing pain or minor injuries, but with no intention of leading to death. It usually starts in the early teens and peaks at mid-adolescence and early adulthood. Some of the most common methods are skin cutting, scratching, biting oneself, picking at wounds, and hair pulling (Tatnell et al., 2018; Cipriano et al., 2020; Giri, 2020; Poudel et al., 2022). Moreover, as per the study of Swannell et al. (2014), as cited in Xiao et al. (2022), there is approximately a 17.2% global lifetime prevalence among school-aged adolescents and young adults.

Globally, there is a high incidence of NSSI among adolescents. Nonetheless, there are differences in terms of motives, means, and severity. Evidence by Xiao et al. (2022) presents that modern society's adolescents have shown a more probable inclination toward NSSI behavior in different ways. Such behaviors are often recurring, and injuries, whether mild or serious, also slowly rise.

Various countries, such as Sweden, Germany, Turkey, Italy, India, China, and Mexico, have reported the occurrence of self-reported NSSI, which are subject to the adopted definition of NSSI, group heterogeneousness, and assessment tools. Nonetheless, developing countries have a dearth of research regarding NSSI (Costa et al., 2021). Although there is an increase in the incidence of self-harm, particularly among emerging adults, most studies focus on suicide and less on NSSI, especially that of senior high school and college students (Mascarinas, 2017).

In the Philippines, a high prevalence of NSSI among adolescents and emerging adults (33.78%) was noted (Galicia & Bautista, 2017). Alarming, this and similar studies suggested that despite its distinction from suicidal attempts, NSSI may increase the risk of successful suicide in the long run through acquired capability. As such, increasing a person's capability to be involved in self-injury is essential when carrying out a suicide plan. NSSI has been described as "a gateway for suicidal attempts." Galicia and Bautista's research (2017) found that 2 to 3 out of 10 who engaged in NSSI are likely to have a suicide attempt later on. This entails the need for early intervention for identifying self-harming behaviors to combat the progression of NSSI to suicide attempts. Alongside this, the implementation of a prevention program is also essential.

The usual age of onset is often within the key developmental transition periods during adolescence. Hence, it was suggested that NSSI often becomes a means of dealing with stressors. Yasgur (2017) emphasized that stressors may be overwhelming for an individual who lacks strong coping mechanisms and a reliable support system. In this case, such individuals may find themselves vulnerable to being overpowered by stress.

As per the findings of AghaMohammadi et al. (2023), in their study on adolescents with NSSI, three common themes, namely vulnerable temperament, traumatic family, and developmental injuries, were derived. Such themes were identified as harmful to a person's self-perception through identified negative emotions and are consistent with the study's overarching theme, "damaged self." Moreover, Xiao et al. (2022) assert that adolescents from single-parent families or who have siblings are relatively more likely to engage in NSSI behavior. This occurrence may be because of a possible failure to adjust to the new family model effectively. Thus, future research must explain the attributes and risk factors of NSSI.

Taylor et al. (2018) pointed out that when NSSI manages difficult thoughts or emotions, it achieves this by enabling individuals to avoid them, replace them with different ones, or directly modify their emotional state. Therefore, it is not surprising that various accounts of persons with NSSI behavior often report a description of a desire to move away or disengage from whatever existing emotional or psychological distress. Some NSSI techniques, such as cutting, were more frequently used by women than by males, but there was no discernible difference for other techniques, like punching. Moreover, other studies (Sornberger et al., 2012; Barrocas et al., 2012) also conclude that NSSI is common among females.

According to Waals et al. (2018), NSSI offers relief on an individual level, and this is often a means to cope with negative feelings such as insecurity, self-doubt, and distress. Moreover, during adolescence, NSSI can be linked to an adolescent's desire for independence, usually from the family and their identity, while still within an attachment relationship. As per Grandclerc et al. (2019), there is a connection between the psychological development of adolescents and self-harm, wherein they assert that self-harm may be a misguided attempt for adolescents to assert their autonomy during this crucial stage. Thus, the complex interaction between the adolescents' and the families' needs makes family involvement integral to the intervention, care, and treatment given to adolescents engaging in NSSI.

Moreover, it has been found that 8.5% of the students who took part in Nemati et al.'s study had NSSI, and those with inadequate family psychological functions had a 13-fold greater chance of doing so than those with high psychological functions. In addition, compared to those with high levels of perceived social support, those with low levels had odds of developing the NSSI that were almost seven times higher.

According to Lewis et al. (2019), NSSI is a prevalent and alarming behavior among university students. College students tend to be vulnerable to engaging in NSSI as it is a period that poses a high risk for its onset (Kiekens et al., 2019). Moreover, Hamza et al. (2021) explained that there are students who cope with the pressures of college by resorting to self-harm, which regulates their negative emotions.

On the other hand, disengagement coping is an adaptation mechanism that presents the degree to which a person responds to stressors by focusing on managing their negative emotions rather than giving a solution to the stressor or problem itself (Shoss, 2016). This is prevalent among teens and often involves attempts to move away from the stressor or the problem situation, either physically, mentally, or psychologically. In a study by Mishra et al. (2023) on coping strategies among undergraduate healthcare students, it was found that female students experiencing psychological distress tended to apply avoidant coping behaviors such as behavioral disengagement. Nonetheless, both male and female students in Saxon et al.'s (2017) study evidenced avoidant coping strategies (i.e., behavioral disengagement, denial) as linked with issues in mental health (i.e., anxiety and depression).

One of the main reasons why students prefer disengagement coping is that it requires less effort compared to active coping strategies (Freire et al., 2020). When faced with a difficult situation, it can be tempting to avoid it altogether rather than expend the energy required to solve the problem, which is supposed to be the right thing to do. This is especially true for students already overwhelmed with academic workloads, personal challenges, and extracurricular activities. Disengagement coping allows students to take a break, breathe fresh air, and avoid the stress and pressure of their daily lives (Smith, 2022).

However, while disengagement coping may temporarily relieve perceived stress, it is unfavorable because it is not an effective long-term solution. Avoiding difficult situations rather than facing them can set off a cycle of avoidance and procrastination that can be difficult to break after a long period (Scott, 2022). If the troubles pile up unresolved, these may snowball into increased stress and anxiety or other mental health concerns with time.

When individuals experience intense emotional pain, they may resort to NSSI as a means of distraction, according to a recent study by Plummer (2023). Disengagement coping strategies, such as withdrawing from social situations, skipping classes, missing academic appointments, avoiding discussions about emotions, or engaging in other behaviors that enable them to avoid confronting their emotional distress, are also commonly employed by individuals who engage in NSSI. A study by Cheng et al. (2022) revealed a significant positive relationship between NSSI and disengagement coping because there is a tendency for individuals who engage in NSSI to apply disengagement coping to cope with emotional distress. Thus, disengagement coping, a negative form of coping, is used to evade or escape from emotions linked to NSSI (e.g., stress, anxiety, depression, and anger.). Instead of addressing the underlying issues, they may find temporary relief or distraction by intentionally inflicting self-injury and focusing on the resulting pain.

Considering the potential dangers of NSSI to young students, the researcher investigated the level of disengagement coping among first-year college students of recollect schools in the Philippines to find out the relationship between disengagement coping and NSSI. Moreover, the extent of NSSI and disengagement coping in the areas of function, practice patterns, and habituation as a whole, and

when they are grouped according to sex, ordinal position, and family structure, was investigated.

Schools, as venues for education, play a critical aspect in youth suicide prevention (Orygen, 2017). As per the findings of Papanikolaou and Almog (2021), it was discovered that students' moral development is positively influenced by faith-based education, which Catholic schools also offer. As for Recollect schools, they are instilled with the Augustinian Recollect style of academic instruction. Recollect education strives to develop students integrally by providing sufficient knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Province of St. Ezekiel Moreno, 2010). Recoletos education, as presented by the Order of Augustinian Recollects (2015), possesses a mission to educate the whole person through holistic education, with a vision that the spiritual values of the Recollect order will guide educational institutions.

This study is anchored on the NSSI Family Distress Cascade Theory by Lisa Waals, wherein it presents the progression of Non-Suicidal Self Injury Behavior in the light of Erik Erikson's psychosocial stages of development and Carter and McGoldrick's family life cycle stages. NSSI Family Distress Cascade Theory identified three stages in the framework of the said behavior: (1) Secrecy, (2) Suspicion, and (3) Disclosure.

This study also aimed to design a viable series of webinars that will encourage students to choose positive, active, and adaptive coping instead of disengaging coping when students run away from their problems. Based on the study's findings, the webinar series also intends to enhance student resilience and build stronger coping resources through increased optimism, psychological mastery, and a wider social support network.

Motivated by personal experience, the researcher, a solo parent who has been doing her best to raise and support her children as they pursue their respective career paths, chose to pursue the present study to contribute to understanding adolescent mental health among Filipinos. Having witnessed the eagerness of her children to thrive in their studies and chosen careers to provide support as they matured in a close-knit family environment, the researcher has the desire to enrich her understanding and further contribute to the existing body of knowledge about familial relationships and coping mechanisms in influencing the mental health of adolescents, shedding light on NSSI behavior and disengagement coping.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior and the level of disengagement coping of students enrolled in Recollect Universities in the Philippines during the first semester of the academic year 2022- 2023. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior of the Recollect university students in the areas of function, practice patterns, and habituation as a whole, and when they are grouped according to:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. ordinal position; and
 - 1.3. family structure?
2. What is the level of disengagement coping of the Recollect University students in the areas of function, practice patterns, and habituation when they are taken as a whole and when they are grouped according to:
 - 2.1. sex;
 - 2.2. ordinal position; and
 - 2.3. family structure?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Recollect university students' non-suicidal self -injury (NSSI) behavior and level of disengagement coping?

Literature Review

NSSI Function, Practice Patterns and Habituation

Meanwhile, NSSI has been associated with a broad array of self-reported functions, including emotion-regulation, self-punishment or communication of distress (Klonsky, 2007). Cutting, skin carving, burning, severe abrading or scratching, punching or hitting, bone breaking, biting, pinching, interfering with wound healing, and (rarely) auto-amputation and ocular enucleation, are only among the various ways individuals may inflict injury to themselves. In an article by Yasgur (2017), he noted that "cutting is the most common, accounting for approximately 70% of patients who self-injure." Furthermore, he also mentioned: "NSSI can be associated with an array of somatic as well as psychiatric health sequelae, and even superficial self-injury may result in serious medical complications." According to Dr. Muehlenkamp, as cited in Yasgur (2017), associate professor of psychology, University of Wisconsin at Eau Claire, self-battery – that is, punching or body part against hard surface to inflict pain – is also common. There are, however, a plethora of ways and means of inflicting injury upon oneself, and it varies from client to client. The reason for engaging in these behaviors vary as well – with emotion regulation as the most common. There are also gender differences in the method of self-injury chosen; where most females resort to cutting, while most males resort to self-battery. Males, however, are less likely to seek help.

The usual age of onset is often within the key developmental transition periods during adolescence. Hence, it was suggested that NSSI often becomes a means of dealing with stressors. "If a person does not have solid coping skills and a good support network, the stressors

may become overwhelming,” Yasgur (2017) mentioned.

Dr. Muehlenkamp further maintained that it is not helpful to assume that self-injury is always undertaken for attention-seeking, which is a common myth. She mentioned further: “The most common reason is emotional regulation, when people are trying to cope with overwhelming distress or self-punishment, which has its origins in self-hatred.” Occasionally, people “try to get others to understand the seriousness of their distress as an outward sign to communicate how much pain they are in.” Elevated levels of negative/unpleasant thoughts and feelings; poor communications skills; poor problem-solving abilities; abuse, mistreatment, hostility, and criticism during childhood; dysfunctional response to stress; the need for self-punishment; and modeling behaviors (e.g., peers, Internet, or the media), are believed to often trigger NSSI among adolescents.

As per the findings of AghaMohammadi et al. (2023) in their study on adolescents with NSSI, three common themes, namely vulnerable temperament, traumatic family, and developmental injuries, were derived. Such themes were identified as harmful to a person's self-perception through identified negative emotions and is consistent with the study's overarching theme, “damaged self.”

While self-injury has been closely linked to suicidal attempts in the past, emerging evidences generated to research increasingly suggests that the two phenomena are “distinct in intent, function, and epidemiology.” It is not in itself a suicide attempt. It is also distinguished from non-fatal suicide attempts. Unlike unsuccessful suicide attempts, which reportedly bring about increased depressive symptoms and psychological distress with regards to failure to obtain a desired outcome, NSSI is ironically associated with decreased negative emotion and increased positive affect. Persons who resort to NSSI often report “feeling better,” or experiencing a “release” or a considerable “relief” from the psychological pressure of overwhelming emotions or experienced frustration which prompted the behavior. This doesn't mean that individuals who engage in NSSI are less suicidal, however; roughly 50% to 85% of individuals who injure themselves have attempted suicide at least once during their lives.

Disengagement Coping

Al-Yateem et al.'s (2020) study revealed that problem-focused disengagement (e.g., problem avoidance, wishful thinking) was commonly used by adolescents aged 12-18 from government and private schools. Results also showed that participants often focused on managing their emotions before solving their problems at school. Meanwhile, the frequent use of self-criticism and denial as coping strategies among soldiers in basic military training, wherein the environment provides low autonomy, is associated with increased mental health issues (Britt, 2016). The relationship between adolescents' coping strategies and inclination to suicidality was investigated by Liang et al. (2020), wherein results revealed that behavioral disengagement was linked to suicidality.

In a study by Mishra et al. (2023) on coping strategies among undergraduate healthcare students, it was found that female students experiencing psychological distress tended to apply avoidant coping behaviors such as behavioral disengagement. Nonetheless, both male and female students in Saxon et al.'s (2017) study evidenced avoidant coping strategies (i.e., behavioral disengagement, denial) as linked with issues on mental health (i.e., anxiety and depression).

One of the main reasons why students prefer disengagement coping is that it requires less effort compared to active coping strategies (Freire et al., 2020). When faced with a difficult situation, it can be tempting to avoid it altogether rather than expend the energy required to solve the problem which is supposed to be the right thing to do. This is especially true for students who are already overwhelmed with academic workloads, personal challenges, and extracurricular activities. Disengagement coping allows students to take a break, take a breath of fresh air, and stay away from the stress and pressure of their daily lives (Smith, 2022).

Another reason why students prefer disengagement coping is that it provides them with a sense of control (Freire et al., 2020). When faced with a problem that seems overwhelming, it can be comforting to know that you have the power to turn down a problem by walking away from it. This can be especially true for students who feel like they have little control over their academic or personal lives. Disengagement coping allows them to take control of the situation by choosing to remove themselves from it, and not to think about the situation at all.

However, while disengagement coping may provide temporary relief from perceived stress, it is not favorable because it is not an effective long-term solution. Avoiding difficult situations rather than facing them can lead to a cycle of avoidance and procrastination that can be difficult to break after a long period of time (Scott, 2022). This can lead to increased stress and anxiety, or other mental health problems over time, as the troubles continue to pile up unresolved.

Sex, Ordinal Position and Family Structure

The researcher considered demographics that are linked to NSSI. In terms of across studies women were significantly more likely to report a history of NSSI than men. Moderator analyses showed that the gender difference was larger for clinical samples, compared to college/community samples. However, there was not a significant relation between age and effect size. Women were more likely to use some methods of NSSI (e.g., cutting) compared to men, but for other methods there was no significant difference e.g., punching (Bresin & Schoenleber, 2015).

In a related study, 8.5% of the students had NSSI experience where the weak family psychological function increased the odds of experiencing the NSSI by 13 times compared to the strong psychological function Besides, the low level of perceived social support

increased the odds of experiencing the NSSI by about 7 times compared to the high perception of social support (Nemati et al., 2020). Low levels of psychological functioning of the families and perception of social support significantly can increase the odds of experiencing the NSSI among adolescents. Therefore, special attention should be paid to these factors in the development of relevant preventive programs in adolescence period, the study concludes.

Family structure and function matters as the prime source from significant others is very crucial to adolescence in their most volatile stage of development.

The present study is anchored on the NSSI Family Distress Cascade Theory by Lisa Waals. The NSSI Family Distress Cascade Theory describes the progression of Non-Suicidal Self Injury Behavior in the light of Erik Erikson's psychosocial stages of development and Carter and McGoldrick's family life cycle stages.

Erik Erikson proposed a series of eight psychosocial stages throughout the lifespan. He believed that in each stage, people experience a conflict that serves as a turning point in development. Adolescents (ages 16 to 20 years old) are in what he referred to as Identity vs. Role Confusion stage, where the need to explore their independence and develop a sense of self becomes even more important. Role confusion results when a weak sense of identity and autonomy is established.

Adolescence is typically associated with shifts in family dynamics in this cycle. "When normal shifts and challenges in family functioning are combined with mental health challenges, such as NSSI, family well-being can flounder" (Waals, 2018). Carter and McGoldrick (1988), in their exploration of dysfunction in relation to normal functioning, noted that problems within the course of the family is a system moving through time. Five stages of the family life cycle were identified: (1) Independence, (2) Coupling or marriage, (3) Parenting: babies through adolescents, (4) Launching adult children, and (5) Retirement or senior years; and focus is set on parenting through adolescence stage, where several findings of previous researches reveal onset and prevalence of most NSSI behavior. NSSI Behavior can interact with the typical developmental challenges of adolescents and therefore make parenting more challenging. Adolescent needs for both autonomy and connectedness, amplified by emotional and hormonal changes, often result in dynamic tension between primary caregivers or family members, especially in cases where there is lack of understanding among caretakers of normative adolescent emotional and social development; hence family equilibrium may appear difficult to obtain at this stage.

NSSI Family Distress Cascade Theory identified three stages in the framework of the said behavior: (1) Secrecy, (2) Suspicion, and (3) Disclosure. In the first stage, adolescents are more likely to keep NSSI hidden from their primary caregivers – this often allows them a sense of autonomy, which we recall, as Erikson would put it, results from the need for a sense of independence as integral in the establishment of personal identity. In the second stage, caregivers may begin to notice that something is happening to their teens, without actually being aware of the self-injuring behaviors. They may "start to ask questions with the aim of understanding the source of their worry or as a means of reassuring themselves that there is not real cause for worry (Waals et al., 2018)." Although well-intended, however, these questions may be viewed as a threat to autonomy by the adolescent, and may encourage them to find further measures to hide their behavior – such as becoming more distant or emotionally cut-off from the concerned caregiver – compromising the need for connectedness, and often adding to further distress. This need for more secrecy and control may amplify parental suspicion, however, resulting to more questioning, which unfortunately prompts the adolescent to take extra measures to conceal behavior. Hence, the less likely for them to seek help. In the third stage, NSSI behavior is often disclosed. Parents often react with controlling behaviors (e.g., checking text messages or grounding their child), upon the discovery of NSSI.

According to Waals et al. (2018), the adolescent may see these reactions as intrusions privacy and overbearing parental hypervigilance as well as a threat to their autonomy, and result in the increase of frequency and severity of the behavior. This process is referred to as complementary schismogenesis or complementary escalation -- escalating processes between the youth and their worried caregivers; describe the development of problems or pathology. "A common feature of these processes is that each of the participants involved view their behavior as the only sensible reaction to the behavior of the other. A common feature of these processes is that "each of the participants involved view their behavior as the only sensible reaction to the behavior of the other." In addition, both participants are often unaware of the overarching pattern in which they push the other to do exactly what they do not want the other to do. Furthermore, "In the case of caregivers, they want reassurance that their child is doing fine, but they push their child into more secret self-injuring behavior as their only means to have a sense of autonomy."

Waals et al. (2018) also stated that NSSI offers relief on an individual level and is often a way of coping with feelings of insecurity, self-doubt, and distress. On a family level, NSSI often plays a part in the adolescent's search for identity and autonomy, within an attachment relationship. This complex interaction between the adolescent's and the family's needs, therefore, makes family involvement integral to the intervention, care, and/or treatment given to adolescents engaging in NSSI.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive and correlational research methods. Descriptive research aimed to provide an accurate and systematic description of variables through the collection, interpretation, and statistical analysis of data, offering a snapshot of the current state of affairs. It focused on the "what" rather than the "how" or "why" of the phenomenon under investigation (Nassaji, 2015) as it sought to

profile first-year students regarding non-suicidal self-injury, examining areas such as function, practice patterns, habituation, and the level of disengagement. Correlational research, on the other hand, aimed to establish statistical relationships between two variables, without significant control over extraneous variables (Price et al., 2021). Specifically, in this study, the researcher aimed to correlate the level of non-suicidal self-injury behaviors in terms of function, practice patterns, and habituation with the level of disengagement coping among the participants.

Participant

Participants of this study consist of Recollect University students from the University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos, University of San Jose-Recoletos - Main Campus, and the University of San Jose - Recoletos - Balamban Campus who have experienced Non-suicidal Self-Injury (NSSI). Only students aged 18-20 and presently in their first year of college were included in the study.

The study participants were determined using the proportional stratified random sampling method. According to Sharma (2017), a stratified random sampling enables the research to make generalizations using the sample from a given population. As such, random samples were then selected from each stratum. The sample size was computed using Slovin's formula $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$ (Slovin, 1960, as cited in Yang, Lin & Hu, 2020) and randomly selected participants from each school based on the computed value.

Based on the computed sample size, the actual number of participants is 391, taken from the total population of 17,338 students from the participating schools. The following page presents the distribution and percentage of the sample population.

Table 1. *Distribution and Percentage of the Sample Population*

Schools	N	%	n
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos	7,541	43.49	170
University of San Jose Recoletos - Main Campus	9,797	56.50	221
University of San Jose Recoletos - Balamban Campus	N/A	N/A	N/A
Total	17,338	100%	391

Instrument

The research instrument has three (3) parts. Part 1 includes the socio-demographic profiles of the participants, specifically the intervening variables needed in the study, such as; (a) sex, (b) ordinal position, (c) family structure, (d) family size, and (c) school. Meanwhile, Part 2 presents the Non-Suicidal Self-Harm Questionnaire, and Part 3 is the Coping Strategies Inventory (Disengagement).

The Non-Suicidal Self-Harm Questionnaire is a research instrument used to measure the extent of non-suicidal self-injury among adolescents. This research study used a researcher-designed questionnaire based on the works of Janis Whitlock and Amanda Purington, The Non-Suicidal Self-Injury Assessment Tool, which is a type of web-based measure of Non-suicidal Self-Injury (NSSI) that was developed in 2005 and was designed for community populations of young adults and is used primarily for research purposes and assesses both primary (form, frequency, and function) and secondary (including but not limited to NSSI habituation, contexts where NSSI is practiced and NSSI when perceived as life interference, treatment, and impacts) NSSI characteristics. In terms of scales, the said instrument covers the following: "Primary and Secondary NSSI characteristics," "Functions," "Recency and Frequency (and age of cessation)," "Age of Onset and Cessation," "Wound Locations," "Initial Motivations," "Severity," "Practice Patterns," "Habituation and Perceived Life Interference," "NSSI Disclosure," "NSSI Treatment Experiences," and "Personal Reflections and Advice" (Whitlock et al., 2014). Specifically, the scales that were used in the study for this part of the research instrument were as follows: (1) Function, (2) Practice Patterns, and (3) Habituation.

The Coping Strategies Inventory by Tobin et al. (1989), particularly the disengagement coping strategies, which was adapted from the questionnaire of Folkman and Lazarus (1981) entitled "Ways of Coping," was used as a basis for the research-designed questionnaire that was used in the study in order to measure the extent of disengagement coping among adolescents. The disengagement subscale comprised strategies that would result in disengaging an individual from the person/environment transaction (Tobin et al., 1989). Scales from this part of the inventory that was used in this study include (a) Problem Avoidance, (b) Wishful Thinking, (c) Social Withdrawal, and (d) Self Criticism.

The instruments underwent testing for validity and reliability.

For validity testing, content and face validity was obtained. Face validity refers to the extent to which a test appears to measure what it is intended to measure or the test items appear. As for face value, it measures what one is seeking to measure (Johnson, 2013). The statements of this validation rating scale were adapted from the criteria for evaluating the questionnaire set forth by Good and Scates (1972). The instrument's content validity can be determined using the viewpoints of the panel of experts. The panel consists of content experts and lay experts. Lay experts were potential research subjects, and content experts were professionals with research experience or work in the field.

For reliability testing, internal consistency reliability shall be employed. Cronbach's alpha measures the internal consistency or reliability between several items, measurements, or ratings. In other words, it estimates how reliable the responses of a questionnaire (or domain of a questionnaire), instrumentation, or rating evaluated by subjects will indicate the stability of the tools (Bujang et al.,

2018).

Procedure

In order to determine the extent of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior and the level of disengagement coping of students enrolled in Recollect Universities in the Philippines during the first semester of the academic year 2022- 2023, the researcher conducted the following procedures:

At the onset, letters requesting permission to conduct this research and with authorized endorsements were sent to each school head for approval. In consideration of the global health risks due to the COVID-19 pandemic, Google Forms were used for the documents instead of the typical paper and pencil method.

Upon approval of the submitted request, the researcher set the testing schedule for data gathering and the administration of research instruments.

The filled-out answer sheets were tabulated, and scores were statistically treated and analyzed.

Data Analysis

To determine the use of an appropriate statistical tool, the researcher employed a normality test to determine the use of either parametric or nonparametric measures of the data.

To determine the level of Non-Suicidal Self-Injury Behavior in the area of function, practice patterns, and habituation, weighted mean was used. The mean is the measure of central tendency derived by computing the sum of all values in the same set so that it summarizes the typical value of that set of data (Condon et al., 2023).

To determine the level of Disengagement Coping, weighted mean was also used.

To determine the relationship between Non-Suicidal Self-Injury Behavior and Disengagement Coping, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was utilized.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to the sending of the questionnaires on three aforementioned Recollect Universities, an informed consent was sent to inform not only the schools but also the participants regarding the nature and process of this study. Consent via google forms was sent to ensure that all involvement of research participants is voluntary. In terms of confidentiality, the researcher ensured the participants that all the gathered responses in this study will be strictly safeguarded. Furthermore, the privacy of the participants was respected by means of withholding the names of the participants at the same time storing all the gathered data in an official storage device secured by the researcher. The data gathered will be destroyed after the analysis of the data to secure confidentiality.

Measures to maintain the participants' wellbeing was also considered. In cases where there is a need to break confidentiality for those who are suicidal, the researcher should take consideration of what is ethically required. During the gathering of data, although participants' suicidal tendency is less likely to be manifested during the gathering of the data due to the absence of face-to-face encounter, risk of imminent harm can happen. Imminent harm is a situation in which a person's risk status is believed to indicate actions that could lead to his or her suicide.

In this case, the researcher's breach of confidentiality happens only if there is an imminent danger to oneself and others. The researcher must be able to identify, or acknowledge signs of imminent danger to participants, and the researcher must have a sense of caring attitude for the participant, and entrust to trusted adults, those who are risking of harming themselves more or are suicidal, and will be kindly informed to withdraw from the study after a referral to mental health worker is made.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Participants

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the participants. When grouped according to school, 93.6% (n=602) are from UNO-R and 6.4% (n=41) are from USJ-R. In terms of sex, 34.5% (n=222) are male students and 65.5% (n=421) are female students. In terms of ordinal position, the eldest has the highest population, 32.7% (n=222), and only child to be the lowest, 13.7% (n=222).

Table 2. *Demographic Profile of the Participants*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
School		
UNO-R	602	93.6
USJR	41	6.4
Sex		
Male	222	34.5
Female	421	65.5
Ordinal Position		

Eldest	210	32.7
Middle	152	23.6
Youngest	193	30.0
Only Child	88	13.7
Family Structure		
Nuclear Family	414	64.4
Extended Family	89	13.8
Single-Parent	115	17.9
Non-traditional Family	25	3.9
Family Size		
3 Family Members and Below	111	17.3
4-6 Family Members	415	64.5
7-9 Family Members	94	14.6
10 or more Family Members	23	3.6
Have you deliberately injured yourself without suicidal intent?		
No	350	54.4
Yes	293	45.6
How do you describe your frequency of resorting to self-harm?		
No Response	4	0.6
Always	17	2.6
Occasionally	112	17.4
Often	119	18.5
Rarely	391	60.8
Total	643	100.0

Extent of Non-suicidal Self-injury (NSSI) Behavior of the Recollect University Students

Table 3 presents the extent of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior of the Recollect University students. The extent of non-suicidal self-injury as a whole (M=2.32, SD=0.83) is low. When grouped according to sex, both male (M=2.27, SD=0.82) and female (M=2.35, SD=0.83) students have low extent of non-suicidal self-injury. All through out the rest of the demographics such as ordinal position and family structure, the Non-Suicidal Self Injury among the participants remained at a low level.

Table 3. Extent of Non-suicidal Self-injury (NSSI) Behavior of the Recollect University Students

Variable	Function			Practice Patterns			Habituation			Non-suicidal Self-injury		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Sex												
Male	2.42	0.87	Lo	1.94	0.87	Lo	2.21	0.99	Lo	2.27	0.82	Lo
Female	2.50	0.86	Lo	1.94	0.89	Lo	2.31	1.07	Lo	2.35	0.83	Lo
Ordinal Position												
Eldest	2.38	0.89	Lo	1.81	0.80	VL	2.24	1.08	Lo	2.24	0.83	Lo
Middle	2.50	0.84	Lo	2.00	0.90	Lo	2.35	1.03	Lo	2.37	0.82	Lo
Youngest	2.43	0.86	Lo	1.92	0.87	Lo	2.21	1.00	Lo	2.28	0.82	Lo
Only Child	2.71	0.81	Mo	2.19	0.99	Lo	2.40	1.06	Lo	2.53	0.83	Lo
Family Structure												
Nuclear Family	2.42	0.85	Lo	1.89	0.82	Lo	2.24	1.00	Lo	2.28	0.80	Lo
Extended Family	2.47	0.94	Lo	1.96	0.99	Lo	2.18	1.02	Lo	2.31	0.89	Lo
Single-Parent	2.66	0.87	Mo	2.15	1.01	Lo	2.54	1.15	Lo	2.53	0.88	Lo
Non-traditional Family	2.35	0.82	Lo	1.69	0.81	VL	2.08	1.06	Lo	2.16	0.75	Lo
Whole	2.47	0.86	Lo	1.94	0.88	Lo	2.28	1.04	Lo	2.32	0.83	Lo

Mean Scale: 1.00-1.80=Very Low (VL), 1.81-2.60=Low (Lo), 2.61-3.40=Moderate (Mo), 3.41-4.20=High (Hi), 4.21-5.00=Very High (VH)

Level of Disengagement Coping of the Recollect University Students

Table 4 presents the level of disengagement coping of the Recollect university students. The level of disengagement coping as a whole (M=3.26, SD=0.74) is moderate. When grouped according to sex, both male (M=3.10, SD=0.71) and female (M=3.35, SD=0.74) students both have moderate levels of disengagement coping. When grouped according to ordinal position, the participants also showed moderate level of disengagement coping; Eldest child (M=3.29; SD=0.76), Middle child (M=3.25; SD=0.76), Youngest (M=3.20; SD=0.76), and Only Child (M=3.39; SD=0.71). The same is also true when the level of disengagement coping is grouped according to family structure, which presented a generally moderate level of disengagement coping. Most family structures, namely, Nuclear family, (M=3.25, SD=0.70), Extended family, (M=3.19, SD=0.84), and Non-traditional family (M=3.03, SD=0.96) were at a moderate level. However, for Single-parent family, disengagement coping was presented as high.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess the normality of the variables. The test revealed that the variables non-suicidal self-injury (KS=0.072, p=0.000) and disengagement (KS=0.036, p=0.048) are not normally distributed, thus, the use of nonparametric test for inferential problem.

Table 4. Level of Disengagement Coping of Recollect University Students

Variable	Problem Avoidance			Wishful Thinking			Social Criticism			Self Withdrawal			Disengagement		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Sex															
Male	3.00	0.69	Mo	3.30	0.91	Mo	3.00	0.96	Mo	3.12	0.96	Mo	3.10	0.71	Mo
Female	3.12	0.75	Mo	3.70	0.94	Hi	3.23	1.06	Mo	3.36	0.96	Mo	3.35	0.74	Mo
Ordinal Position															
Eldest	3.02	0.77	Mo	3.60	0.98	Hi	3.23	1.06	Mo	3.30	0.99	Mo	3.29	0.76	Mo
Middle	3.08	0.69	Mo	3.56	0.89	Hi	3.13	1.00	Mo	3.25	0.90	Mo	3.25	0.70	Mo
Youngest	3.10	0.72	Mo	3.51	0.97	Hi	3.02	1.04	Mo	3.17	0.96	Mo	3.20	0.76	Mo
Only Child	3.18	0.69	Mo	3.59	0.94	Hi	3.27	1.01	Mo	3.51	0.99	Hi	3.39	0.71	Mo
Family Structure															
Nuclear	3.06	0.72	Mo	3.56	0.89	Hi	3.15	1.01	Mo	3.24	0.91	Mo	3.25	0.70	Mo
Extended	3.01	0.77	Mo	3.51	1.01	Hi	3.09	1.14	Mo	3.16	1.08	Mo	3.19	0.84	Mo
Single-Parent	3.20	0.69	Mo	3.75	0.99	Hi	3.26	1.01	Mo	3.49	0.99	Hi	3.42	0.74	Hi
Non-traditional	3.07	0.92	Mo	2.97	1.24	Mo	2.82	1.10	Mo	3.27	1.19	Mo	3.03	0.96	Mo
Whole	3.08	0.73	Mo	3.56	0.95	Hi	3.15	1.04	Mo	3.27	0.96	Mo	3.26	0.74	Mo

Mean Scale: 1.00-1.80=Very Low (VL), 1.81-2.60=Low (Lo), 2.61-3.40=Moderate (Mo), 3.41-4.20=High (Hi), 4.21-5.00=Very High (VH)

Significant Relationship Between the Recollect University Students’ Non-Suicidal Self-injury (NSSI) Behavior and Level of Disengagement Coping

Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship between the Recollect University students’ non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior and level of disengagement coping. As presented in table 5, findings reveal that there is a significant relationship between the Recollect University students’ non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) behavior and level of disengagement coping [rs(641)=0.394, p=0.000] at 95% level of confidence. This implies that the more students would resort to NSSI, the higher their tendency to take refuge in disengagement coping.

Table 5. Significant Relationship Between the Recollect University Students’ Non-Suicidal Self-injury (NSSI) Behavior and Level of Disengagement Coping

Variable	rs	df	p
Non-suicidal Self-injury x Disengagement	0.394*	641	0.000

Low Levels of NSSI among Participants

Foremost, as per the findings presented in table 3, the participants showed a low level of NSSI behavior. This supports the study of Kiekens et al. (2023) that claimed a significant portion of first-year students as not engaging in NSSI behavior despite the study emphasizing NSSI as a major concern in colleges across the globe. The participants engage in self-harm but at a low level and one of the contributing factors may be peer modeling. Adolescents who hear that other peers have engaged in self-harm could be more likely to engage in similar harmful behaviors. It is important for parents and educators to engage in open conversations about mental health challenges and self-harm so that they might be better guided toward healthier coping strategies. Teenagers are easily swayed by the behavior of their peers, and this sort of influence applies to acts of self-harm and other negative coping skills for mental illness (White, 2020).

According to Waals (2018), NSSI offers relief on an individual level and is often a way of coping with feelings of insecurity, self-doubt, and distress. On a family level, NSSI often plays a part in the adolescent’s search for identity and autonomy, within an attachment relationship. This complex interaction between the adolescent’s and the family’s needs, therefore, makes family involvement integral to the intervention, care, and/or treatment given to adolescents engaging in NSSI.

In light of a 2020 study in Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica, it considered the notion of self-harm in adolescents a "social contagion" (Syed et al., 2020). Moreover, groupthink plays a stronger role in adolescence than in adult years. The reason for this difference is the power of peers, i.e. 'peer pressure' during the pre-teen and teen years”. While those who partake in nonsuicidal self-injury, or NSSI, do not always have a desire to die, the percentage of adolescents who are suicidal are higher within the group that engages in NSSI than those who do not (Brown, 2019).

Even though the results in this current study show that the prevalence of NSSI among the participants is low, this should not be taken for granted because the low level of NSSI activity among students does not mean self-injury is at all non-existent. In light of Syed et al (2020) study, awareness of a friend's self-injury was associated with an adolescent’s own involvement with NSSI, suicidal ideation,

and suicide attempts and the data showed that inclination to engage with NSSI for youth was apparent especially who were diagnosed with or met criteria for mental health disorders.

Self-injury by peers as a “social contagion” is evidenced by data from 1,483 youth in Ontario, Canada between the ages of 14 and 17 who engaged in a digital self-report survey surrounding mental health and self-injury, with their parents providing demographic information (Syed et al., 2020). Findings show that when it comes to coping skills, family and peer support are especially relevant to adolescents since it is a developmental stage that surrounds dynamic transitions in social networks (Tunyu Xiao in White, 2020).

Further, there is a moderate level of disengagement coping across sex, ordinal position, and family structure in this study as presented in table 4. In terms of gender, there is no significant difference for males and females in most of the coping strategies, including disengagement coping, and moderate levels of disengagement coping are shown as a response to college transition (Mustafa, 2024; Dalton & Hammen, 2018). Meanwhile, Diefenderfer's study (2022) shed light on the stress coping responses of college students, despite their respective backgrounds, which revealed the prevalence of disengagement coping strategies before and even during the pandemic.

But what stands out is the high level of disengagement coping among students living with a single parent. The moderate level of behavior in disengagement coping is noteworthy, but the high level of disengagement coping exists when students are nurtured under the care of a single parent. This is the finding presented in table 4 and supports the conclusion of Rajgariah et. al. (2021) that students who belong to a single-parent family may be more prone to disengagement coping for several reasons. Just as the probable reasons why students tend to engage in disengagement coping when confronted with a problem is an important question to consider as shown in the findings of the current study. Disengagement coping entails avoiding confrontation with the threat or the related distress. This includes responses such as avoidance, denial, and wishful thinking. Pawlak et al (2021) stressed that disengagement coping is often emotion-focused because it typically involves an attempt to escape feelings of distress. Learners often undergo elevated degrees of apprehension, tension, and sadness, boredom, and they document a great degree of deconstructive thoughts and feelings.

Moreover, disengagement coping as a type of coping mechanism that involves withdrawing from a situation or problem, rather than actively trying to solve it is often used by students who are confronted with academic difficulty or personal dilemmas that they feel they are unable to overcome. It is in these times that they perceive a psychological and emotional threat, and students think they cannot cope with the threat. While disengagement coping may provide a considerable amount of temporary relief from stress or other uncomfortable and unwanted emotions, it is not an effective long-term solution.

Exploring the reasons why students prefer disengagement coping and why it is important to find more effective coping mechanisms are very significant reference points in helping students cope properly and positively, and successfully.

Another reason why students prefer disengagement coping is that it provides them with a sense of control (Freire et al., 2020). When faced with a problem that seems overwhelming, it can be comforting to know that you have the power to turn down a problem by walking away from it. This can be especially true for students who feel like they have little control over their academic or personal lives. Disengagement coping allows them to take control of the situation by choosing to remove themselves from it, and not to think about the situation at all.

However, while disengagement coping may provide temporary relief from perceived stress, it is not favorable because it is not an effective long-term solution. Avoiding difficult situations rather than facing them can lead to a cycle of avoidance and procrastination that can be difficult to break after a long period of time (Scott, 2022). This can lead to increased stress and anxiety, or other mental health problems over time, as the troubles continue to pile up unresolved.

Hence it is very important for students to find more effective coping mechanisms that will allow them to address their problems in a constructive way. Active coping strategies, such as problem-solving, optimism, and seeking social support, can help students proactively feel more in control of their lives and reduce stress levels (Wu et al., 2020). Even though strategies require more effort than disengagement coping, but they are more likely to lead to long-term solutions.

Therefore, while disengagement coping may provide temporary relief from stress, it is not an effective long-term solution for students. It is important for students to find ways for more effective coping mechanisms that will allow them to address their problems in a constructive way. Active coping strategies, that are solution-focused, optimistic, and purpose-driven can help students to feel more in control of their lives and reduce stress levels. By finding more effective coping mechanisms, students can build resilience over time and develop the skills they need to succeed in school and in life (Ronen, 2021).

As indicated in the findings of the current study, students have the tendency to do disengagement coping at low, moderate, and high levels because doing it is a lot easier than active coping, that is, finding probable solutions concerning the troubles at hand is evidence validated in other related research. Participants tend to do NSSI as they disengage from stressors (Prayeti & Widyatno, 2022). When students disengage, doing NSSI can also be part of their disengaging coping mechanism as shown in the results of this current study.

As spelled out in the related literature, non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) is a type of behavior that involves intentionally causing harm to oneself without the intention of committing suicide. NSSI is often used as a coping mechanism to deal with emotional distress, and it is considered a form of disengagement coping. This is because NSSI involves withdrawing from the situation or problem, rather than actively trying to solve it.

People who engage in NSSI may do so to regulate their emotions. When faced with intense emotional distress, such as feelings of sadness, anxiety, or anger, they may feel overwhelmed and unable to cope. NSSI can provide them with temporary relief from these emotions by creating a physical sensation that distracts them from the emotional pain they are experiencing (Prussien, Rosenblum, & Whitlock, 2023). NSSI in this way can be seen as a form of disengagement coping, as the individual is withdrawing from the emotional distress rather than actively trying to solve it.

NSSI can also be used as a way to gain a sense of control. When faced with situations or problems that feel overwhelming or out of control, engaging in NSSI can provide a sense of power and control over one's body (Hetrick, et al., 2020). This can be considered as a form of disengagement coping, as the individual is redirecting his or her focus from the situation or problem and focusing instead on his or her own body and physical sensations, that is, inflicting self-injury.

However, as mentioned earlier, while NSSI may provide temporary relief from emotional or physical distress, it is not an effective long-term solution. Engaging in NSSI can lead to physical harm and can also perpetuate the cycle of emotional distress or even lead to a suicide attempt or completion. Thus, training students how to build stronger coping resources is very important so that they will be equipped with the knowledge and skills on effective coping rather than running away from their problems. Disengaging or running away from distress is not a long-term solution, rather building healthy and positive coping mechanisms is preferable as it offers lasting solutions to problems.

Higher Levels of Disengagement Coping Among Students Living with Single-Parents

The second finding shows that students who belong to a family structure with a single parent have higher levels of disengagement coping. This finding leads to a question of why students who belong to a single-parent family are prone to have higher disengagement coping.

As per Rajgariah et al. (2021), there are several reasons, and the first is maybe a lack of emotional support. Single-parent families may have limited emotional support due to the absence of one parent, and the single mother or father, or even guardian raising the child may also have a share of their own emotional deficiencies. The result is that this can lead to feelings of loneliness and isolation, making it even more difficult for students to cope with the stress and challenges that come their way.

Another reason is financial stress because single-parent families may face financial burdens due to the absence of a second income from a spouse (Kim & Kim, 2020). This can lead to students feeling overwhelmed and unable to focus on their studies as they think about how they are going to pay for a school project, transportation, food, and the like. The third one could be increased responsibilities. Students from single-parent families may have increased responsibilities, such as taking care of younger siblings or helping with household chores, or even working while studying to make both ends meet. This can lead to a lack of time and energy to focus on schoolwork, leading to disengagement in coping when overwhelmed with stressors around them.

The last one could also be the lack of role models. Students from single-parent families may lack positive role models (Watt, 2019), that is mother-absent or father-absent families, making it difficult for them to develop effective coping strategies. This can lead to disengagement coping to avoid dealing with stress and challenges whenever insurmountable situations come around. As mentioned earlier, disengagement coping is easier than a solution-focused or active coping strategy because it simply offers an easy way out because the person is already overwhelmed to expend energy on the challenge at hand.

Overall, students from single-parent families may be more prone to disengagement coping due to a lack of emotional support, financial stress, increased responsibilities, and a lack of positive role models (Johnson, 2022). Hence it is important not just for educators and guidance counselors, but also parents to provide support and resources to help these students develop effective coping strategies and succeed academically. Indeed, it is evident that parents also have a vital role in the process. Enhancing a wider social support network among students could also be of help.

Significant Relationship Between NSSI and Disengagement Coping

As evidenced in the findings of the current study, there is a significant relationship between disengagement coping and NSSI at $r=.394$ at 95% confidence level and has the strength of medium correlation. This means that students having a disengagement coping strategy have the tendency to self-injure and is not born by chance. Results show that NSSI behaviors among students are low across sex, ordinal position, and family structure. And low is still a quantitative basis that students do some NSSI. And this self-injury as a means of avoidant coping correlates with their disengagement coping.

There is a significant positive relationship between NSSI and disengagement coping because individuals who engage in NSSI may use disengagement coping as a way to cope with their emotional distress, which is aligned with the findings of Cheng et al. (2022). As mentioned earlier, NSSI is often associated with negative emotions such as stress, anxiety, depression, and anger, and individuals who engage in NSSI may use disengagement coping as a way to avoid or escape from these emotions and relish the pain instead, to help them distracted by inflicting injury to themselves.

An individual who is experiencing intense emotional pain, for instance, may engage in NSSI as a way to distract themselves from their emotions (Plummer, 2023). They may also use disengagement coping by withdrawing from social situations, being absent from class,

and not showing up to academic appointments such as reporting, avoiding talking about their emotions or engaging in other behaviors that help them avoid confronting their emotional distress.

Additionally, research has shown that individuals who engage in NSSI may lack emotional intelligence and it is difficult for them in regulating their emotions so they may use disengagement coping to deal with their upsetting feelings. Individuals with a lifetime history of self-injuries had significantly higher levels of depression, anxiety, and impulsivity as well as significantly lower levels of emotional intelligence and self-esteem (Masłowska et al., 2021). Once again, disengagement coping may provide temporary relief from emotional distress, but it is not a healthy or effective long-term coping strategy.

Hence, the positive relationship between NSSI and disengagement coping highlights the need for individuals who engage in NSSI to learn healthy coping strategies that can help them regulate their emotions and manage their distress in a more effective way. Therapy, psychoeducational activities, focused group sessions, and other forms of mental health support can be helpful in teaching individuals healthy coping strategies and addressing the underlying emotional issues that may contribute to NSSI.

Conclusions

NSSI may still be a taboo topic but is being gradually given attention especially with the rise of mental health campaigns and increased access to professional help. The present study proved the low prevalence of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) and disengagement coping strategies among first year Recollect students. Its prevalence is common among adolescents, particularly during the transition from high school to college with due consideration of the challenges and experiences they encounter with adolescence. Awareness of this prevalence, despite being relatively low, is crucial to provide preventive and proactive measures since even non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) and disengagement coping strategies among college students. The school has a crucial role in the promotion of student welfare, wherein the members of the school community have a significant contribution. Despite the relatively low prevalence of NSSI, its existence should not be ignored; preventive and proactive measures are crucial to address it. The study's findings could be a possible reference point for school administrators to enhance student services that will cater to students' academic and psychosocial needs. Recollect school administrators can be a considerable influence in cascading awareness of the harms NSSI can do to students and curb, if not eradicate, NSSI by creating policies that will prevent students from resorting to NSSI and disengaging coping mechanisms.

There are several other contributing factors that need to be considered and peer influence could be one. An example would be a student's exposure to any form of NSSI by peers, which may increase the probability of engaging in such a manner. This could also then be linked to their search for identity and autonomy within family relationships since they are in their adolescent years. This, in turn, shed light on the significance of observation, sensitivity, and communication in school as well as at home. At school, both teachers and guidance counselors could contribute to combating the likelihood of NSSI and disengagement coping among students. Since teachers are the ones who have the most contact hours with students, they can observe and spot maladaptive behaviors which can be a viable means of helping students avoid and make referrals to the guidance office for counseling and proper interventions. As for guidance counselors, they can maximize their capacity to revitalize guidance services. This can be done by making this study a springboard to strengthen students' building of their stronger coping resources by giving them the tools on how to convert disengagement coping into an active or engagement coping for a long-term solution to their problems, as well as conducting psychological education among students who self-injure. Meanwhile, parents should be vigilant in guiding their children, especially those who are exhibiting behaviors akin to NSSI and take an active involvement in nurturing healthier relationships with them, and provide the necessary guidance and support to understand where these behaviors are likely coming from and eventually come up with more effective strategies of helping.

Both NSSI and disengagement coping offer temporary relief and are not an effective long-term solution since it involves avoiding problems instead of actively addressing them. Engaging in such behavior may lead to a cycle of avoidance that could negatively impact the coping and lifestyle of students. However, the findings reveal a relatively high level of disengagement coping among students from single-parent families which may suggest the significance of support systems, especially at home. It also presents a potential vulnerability for students with this family, wherein prevalence of disengagement coping may imply a need for interventions for this population. Attention to this is recommended to address this issue since this may suggest the impact of support systems, whether within the family or external resources, as a buffer for challenges of adolescence especially with the transition to college.

The positive correlation between NSSI and disengagement coping suggests that students who use disengagement coping have a higher likelihood of engaging in NSSI. Nonetheless, despite being a risk factor, it should be noted that correlation does not equal causation; thus, it doesn't fully guarantee that one will engage in NSSI because they engage in disengagement coping since there are other factors that should be considered. Indeed, it is crucial for students to seek help from school's helping professionals where they can consciously change maladaptive ways of coping into adaptive ones, become aware of the benefits of active and positive coping, and overcome the stigma attached to seeking professional help when needed in order to conquer their NSSI behaviors and redirect their disengaging coping strategies. The study signifies the need for the students' engagement of active coping mechanisms, which is more effective in terms of long-term solutions.

Future research could explore more in-depth reasons behind the higher disengagement coping levels among students from single-parent families, which could pave the way to further understanding the findings of the present research. Moreover, delving deeper into knowing the tendencies of students other than resorting to NSSI when they utilize disengagement coping strategies as well as

investigating other variables and methodologies would contribute to existing literature.

NSSI is not just a trend and a simple thing that must be taken for granted. It is a very serious problem that is concerned with the mental and emotional health of the people who may be ok on the outside but are suffering and in pain deep inside. The same goes with disengagement coping, which may be a manifestation of something that goes beyond what meets the eyes. So, instead of adding negativities over and above to what they are currently feeling, be their companion and filled them with love, patience, understanding and compassion because as to what the poet Victor Hugo said, “Even the darkest night will end and the sun will rise” which means that even in the darkest times and worst situations, there is still hope that awaits your path the next day.

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